

THE INFLUENCE OF FERTILIZERS ON THE ECOLOGICAL CONDITION OF THE LIGHT GRAY SOILED SOIL OF THE FOREST ZONE

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ABSTRACT

The results of research into the ecological state of the light-gray podzolized soil of the Polissia zone, namely, the cellulolytic activity on the example of the decomposition of linen fabric depending on the fertilizer, are presented.

The introduction of straw, siderates, and manure during the cultivation of corn contributed to the active decomposition of cellulose up to 67,4%

Keywords: corn, siderates, manure, linen cloth.

Introduction. The biological activity of the soil is determined by the reserves of humus in it. According to the publications of scientific articles, the amount of humus in the soil has decreased dramatically in recent years. Therefore, in order to obtain a high and high-quality harvest, it is necessary to apply a sufficient amount of organic fertilizers [2].

Taking into account the sharp decrease in manure production in the farms of the Polissia zone and the high cost of mineral fertilizers when growing corn on light-gray podzolized soil, it is not possible to apply their recommended norms, which, in turn, requires the search for alternative sources of organic mass entering the soil, which would contribute not only to obtain high yields, but also to increase soil fertility.

At the same time, a special place belongs to the use of straw and siderates when growing corn [1].

Formulation of the problem. It is currently not possible to provide agricultural crops with organic fertilizers to the full extent, and therefore, as fertilizers, it is possible to use the by-products of the predecessor - the straw of grain crops and intermediate crops of agricultural crops using their green mass for siderate [4].

Along with the root and harvest residues of plants, the additional application of straw and siderates to the soil is the main source of soil enrichment for organic matter.

It is recommended to use straw as an organic fertilizer during the harvesting of grain crops [5]. To prevent immobilization of nitrogen from the soil when applying straw, it is recommended to apply nitrogen fertilizers at the rate of 8-12 kg of nitrogen for each ton of straw, giving preference to ammonia and amide forms of mineral fertilizers. The crushed mass of straw is mixed with the upper layer of the soil with disc tools, as a result of which a loose mulching layer is created, which improves the air exchange of the soil, prevents the formation of a soil crust, reduces the washing of the soil, contributes to the accumulation of moisture in it, and prevents the loss of nutrients [2].

It is recommended to use annual and perennial leguminous crops, cabbage, cereals for green fertilizers, depending on zonal characteristics. Plant mass is partially or completely wrapped in the soil at the place of its cultivation to enrich it with organic matter, mineral elements and improve agrophysical properties [3].

The products of the decay of the green mass should be used by the next crop, and this can be achieved by plowing the siderate in late autumn. The decay of the green mass occurs in the spring with the onset of heat directly under the cultivated crop [4].

Plants placed after siderates produce higher quality products, especially corn. When using siderates, the soil does not overheat or dry out, microorganisms and earthworms actively work in it, which work to enrich the arable layer with humus.

At the same time, there is an increase in the biological activity of the soil by 1,5-2 times [5].

An important factor in the activation of the vital activity of the soil is the presence of mesofauna in it, where biological activity reflects the complex of biological processes of the soil and acts as an important indicator of changes in agrophysical and agrochemical properties of soil fertility, indicates the conditions of nutrition and growth and development of plants and, ultimately, the level of soil fertility [2].

In the context outlined above, soil and biological research is a necessary component of technological solutions for optimizing the structure of land use, improving crop cultivation technologies based on the maximum use of the biological potential of the soil and obtaining a guaranteed and high-quality harvest [1]. Therefore, the purpose of the research was to study the biological activity of the soil during the cultivation of corn on light-gray podzolized soil in the Polissya zone.

Tasks of research. In order to achieve the set goal and task of the research, it was to study the intensity of biological processes of the soil depending on the application of fertilizers during the cultivation of corn.

Research objects and methods. Changes in the biological activity of light-gray cellulose-destroying microorganisms depending on the use of fertilizers during corn cultivation.

Research was conducted during 2020-2022 at the research field of the Polissia National University. The soil is a light-gray gilded sandy loam on loess-like loam.

The soil layer of 0-20 cm is characterized by the following agrochemical parameters: the content of humus is 1,22-1,35%, the reaction of the soil solution is moderately acidic (pH 4,8-4,9), the amount of absorbed bases and the degree of soil saturation with bases are low and consist of respectively, 1,80-2,07 mg-equiv./100g of soil and 46,5-53,2%, the content of mobile forms of nitrogen and phosphorus is average, potassium is low.

By-products of cereals - straw, sider fertilizer - oil radish, manure, mineral fertilizers were used.

The scheme of the experiment included the following fertilizer options:

1. Without fertilizers (control)
2. Mineral fertilizers $N_{60}P_{40}K_{70}$
3. Straw (3 t/ha) + N_{10} per 1 ton of straw + siderates 12 t/ha + manure 40 t/ha + $N_{60}P_{40}K_{70}$.

The biological activity of the soil was determined according to generally accepted methods (linen cloths). The technology of growing corn is generally accepted for the zone.

Statistical processing of the experimental material was carried out using the MS Excel program.

Research results. One of the important indicators of the biological activity of the soil is the intensity of its fiber breakdown by microorganisms. Since decay is determined by the presence of available forms of nitrogen, phosphorus and other plant nutrients in the soil, the measure of cellulolytic activity reflects the general picture of microbiological processes.

Microflora takes an active part in soil processes, namely, with their participation, the decay of plant remains occurs, humus formation processes are carried out.

That is, the transformation of organic matter by microorganisms determines the biological activity of the soil.

Research has established that the cellulolytic activity of the light-gray opizolized soil, using the example of the destruction of linen fabric, was significantly dependent on fertilizer. The obtained research results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1.

Destruction of linen fabric in light-gray podsolized soil depending on the fertilizer

Fertilizer options	Years of research				
	2020	2021	2022	Average for 2020-2022	
				% tissue decay	% to control
1. Control (without fertilizers)	15,3	12,5	53,2	27,2	100,0
2. Mineral fertilizers $N_{60}P_{40}K_{70}$	28,9	23,8	67,6	40,1	148,5
3. Straw (3 t/ha) + N_{10} per 1 ton of straw + siderates 12 t/ha + manure 40 t/ha + $N_{60}P_{40}K_{70}$	59,2	33,4	83,2	58,6	217,0
$NIR_{0,5}$, %	7,2	3,6	18,7		

Research has established that the activity of cellulose-destroying organisms under corn in different versions of fertilizer is not the same. The lowest percentage of tissue decay was observed in the control version (without fertilizers) and was only 27,2 %.

Application of both mineral and organic fertilizers contributed to the activation of cellulose-destroying microorganisms in the soil. In the version where only mineral fertilizers were applied, the tissue decay was 40,1%.

The most intensive microbiological processes occurred in the variant where the introduction of straw, siderates, manure and mineral fertilizers was combined.

The decay of the fabric in this case reached 58,6%, or 2,15 times more compared to the control variant.

It should be noted that the hydrothermal conditions of the year significantly influenced the process of cellulose decomposition.

In 2020 and 2021, less activity of cellulose-degrading microorganisms was observed compared to 2022, namely by 1,4-2,5 times, and in the control version (without fertilizers) by 3,4-4,2 times.

This is due to the less favorable weather conditions of these years for the activity of microorganisms in the soil.

Conclusions. The ecological condition of light-gray podsolized soil during corn cultivation indicates that its biological activity is not the same and depends on fertilizer.

The highest activity of cellulose-destroying microorganisms was observed when straw - 3 t/ha, siderates - 12 t/ha, manure - 40 t/ha and mineral fertilizers $N_{60}P_{40}K_{70}$ were applied to the soil, where the decomposition of linen fabric reached 58,6%.

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